

INTRODUCING INTELLECTUAL MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENTS TO PRODUCTION PROCESSES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

Yusupova, Nozima Khosilbek kizi

of 1st year master

Nozimaumirova308@gmail.com

Ungarov Dzhakhongir Yuldash ugli

is a master of the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute. Phone number:+9989 916306704;

jahongirungarov7@gmail.com

Shertaylakov Gayrat Murodovich

a master of the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute.

Phone number:+9989 916306704; gayratshertaylaqov509@gmail.com

Annotation: The article describes quality and product quality. The effectiveness of measures to improve the quality of their products was discussed. The article argues that improving the quality of agricultural products will serve to fully meet the needs of the population in food, increase the efficiency of agricultural production.

Key phrases: Own standard, test, calibrate, label, export, Own DST, modification.

Automation of production processes and provision of intelligent measuring tools based on international standards is one of the main directions of technical development and is the main factor that serves to continuously increase production efficiency and raise product quality to a high level. Undoubtedly, the most responsible work in providing automation production processes with intelligent measuring tools falls on the engineering and technical personnel. Ensuring the effective operation of measuring equipment is a daily problem of metrologists [1].

Today's engineers must be able to use new technologies and techniques, to widely introduce automation of technological processes, to identify and accelerate production reserves. In particular, engineers and metrologists have the responsible task of being pioneers of scientific and technical development [2].

Measuring equipment is one of the important factors of scientific and technical progress in all spheres of the national economy. In recent years, the speed of transition of technological processes has increased, the number of parameters measured in one unit has increased [3]. Therefore, the reliability of measuring devices and information-measurement systems in many cases determines the overall reliability of the aggregate. Without knowing the correct values of the parameters and without automatic control of these values, it is impossible to control technological processes or aggregates correctly, and without measuring tools, it is impossible to automate [4].

In order to widely introduce measurement techniques into production, every engineer-technician, regardless of what field he is a specialist in, should be aware of the basics of metrology, technological measurement methods and tools, and the possibilities of using computer technology in the automation of measurement processes. is necessary [5].

The automatic adjustment system (Fig. 1, v) is designed to maintain the value of one or more physical quantities of the adjustment object RO, which characterizes the production process, with a given accuracy. In addition, ART can change the value of the indicated quantity according to the given law [6].

Let's take a closer look at the construction principles of ARTs. The construction of ART is based on a number of general adjustment principles, such as deviation adjustment, perturbation adjustment, mixed (combined) adjustment, and flexibility principles [7].

The principle of automatic adjustment determines the type of adjustment effects affecting the adjustment object and what information is based on them. One of the main features describing the adjustment principle is the working information needed

to develop the adjustment effect and the structure of their transfer to the system. Adjustment by deviations is also called the Polzunov-Watt principle and is explained by the scheme in Fig. 2, a, consisting of two main parts connected by a chain of interaction [8]: the adjustment object RO and the adjuster R finds The parameter being adjusted is compared with the assigned value. A corrective effect is developed based on the difference of these two values. The deviation of the adjustment system or the so-called error should not exceed the specified value [9]. Then a complete relationship is established between the parameter being adjusted and the set value, and the parameter can be controlled by changing the magnitude [10].

In order to compare the current value of the variable being adjusted with its assignment value, this parameter is supplied from the output of the adjustment object to the input of the adjuster (comparison element to SE), resulting in a closed contour of the transfer of influences. This feedback circuit is called the main or main feedback, because in general some elements (especially the regulator) can have additional internal feedback to improve the performance of the ART [11]. The parameter being adjusted is fed to the input of the adjuster through the main feedback with an inverse reference to the input effect. Therefore, the main feedback is negative, in which the system elements give the output magnitude to its input, weakening the effect of the input magnitude on the output. If the output magnitude given to the input of the system element increases the effect of the input magnitude on the output, then such feedback is considered positive [12].

Feedback effects are divided into hard and soft types according to the nature of transmission. Hard feedback affects both equilibrium and transients, while soft feedback affects only transients and ceases to affect equilibrium [13].

An object of adjustment or control is an open system, which means that it is under dynamic interaction with the external environment. The influence of the external environment on the object of adjustment or control has an uncontrollable character and is represented by a random change in its state. The effects of the environment on the object of adjustment or control are called disturbance effects

[14]. The principle of disturbance adjustment or control has been proposed to eliminate external influences. The essence of the disturbance adjustment or control principle (or the compensation principle) is to select one main one affecting the ART from the various disturbances affecting the system (Fig. 2, b). In this case, the effect of the main disturbance on the parameter being adjusted is compensated, and the adjustment effect is developed based on the results of measuring the main disturbance affecting the object [15].

References:

1. Isroilov F. M., Rakhmonov F. A., ugli Ungarov D. Y. HIGH RESPONSIBILITY (SENSITIVITY) AND ACCURACY OF TEMPERATURE SENSORS FACTORS OF ACHIEVEMENT AND RELIABLE OPERATION //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – S. 163-169.
2. Abduxakimovich R. F. et al. ISO 14000 SERIYALI XALQARO STANDARTLAR BO'YICHA EKOLOGIK MENEJMENT TIZIMI VA ATROF-MUHITNI BOSHQARISHNING XALQARO STANDARTLARI //World scientific research journal. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2. – S. 20-26.
3. Isroilov F. M. et al. O 'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA SIFAT MENEJMENTI TIZIMLARIGA O 'RNATUVCHI MEYORIY STANDART TALABLAR //Studencheskiy vestnik. – 2021. – №. 21-10. – S. 70-72.
4. SHertaylaqov G'. M., O'ng'arov J. Y. XALQARO STANDARTLAR MIQYOSIDA MUVOFIQLIKNI BAHOLASH FAOLIYATDA ISO 9001: 2008 STANDARTI BILAN ISO 9001: 2015 STANDARTI TAHLILI //World scientific research journal. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2. – S. 27-38.
5. Ganisherovich B. A. et al. THE ROLE OF WIDE EXPORTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – S. 99-101.
6. Исматуллаев П. Р. и др. Разработка автоматических влагомеров для продуктов агропромышленного комплекса //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 4. – С. 44-46.
7. Shertaylakov G. M. THE METHOD OF PERFORMING NONSTANDARD LABORATORY WORKS IN PHYSICS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2020. – T. 8. – №. 3.
8. Shertaylakov G. M. Some Aspects of Teaching Physics at School //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2019. – №. 1.
9. Шертайлаков Г. М. и др. Понятие о измерении //Молодой ученый. – 2017. – №. 6. – С. 100-102.
10. Шертайлаков Г. М., Уралов Г. А. Поверка средств измерения //Техника. Технологии. Инженерия. – 2018. – №. 2. – С. 6-8.
11. O'g B. O. N. et al. The role of quality management system in increasing product quality in enterprises //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 12. – С. 228-233.

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE " INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"

2023 Munchen, (Germany)

12. BADALOV U. N. O. THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 163-169.

13. Juraboevich B. N. Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 117-118.

14. BADALOV N. J. O. R. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES WITH A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 146-156.

15. Jo'raboyevich B. N. ROLE OF COMPARISON, CALIBRATION AND METROLOGICAL CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 168-175.